

Taming growth

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How many ways are there to bend cubic growth beyond the origin down to eventually zero?

The simplest taper

$$ex(x) = e^{-x}$$

works well; the OCTAVE code

```
r=.001;;x=0:r:14;;ex=exp(-x);,exc=ex.*(x.^3);
```

produced the tapered-cubic image below.

Planck used the variant

$$p(x) = 1/(e^x - 1)$$

which also works well; of course, this became later the Bose-Einstein factor. Other variations on the decaying exponential theme include the Fermi-Dirac taper

$$f(x) = 1/(e^x + 1)$$

the Hyperbolic secant

$$hs(x) = \operatorname{sech}(x) = 2/(e^x + e^{-x})$$

and cosecant

$$hc(x) = \operatorname{csch}(x) = 2/(e^x - e^{-x})$$

All these tapers are adept at taming cubic growth; how can they be compared?

The tapered cubics may be regarded as density functions in their own right; as such, their distribution functions may be estimated; in OCTAVE code for the exponential case:

```
dexc=cumsum(exc);,dexc=dexc/max(dexc); % Exponential decay distribution shown below
```


From here the (base 2) Shannon entropy

$$-\sum(dist)\log_2(dist)$$

provides a numerical comparison of the five distributions, and therefore the tapering methods themselves; results are tabulated below.

Exponential: 2.2541

Planck: 2.2873

Fermi-Dirac: 2.2456

Hyperbolic secant: 2.2393

Hyperbolic cosecant: 2.2787

Thus the Planck distribution is the most entropic, hence the most informative; an unexpected (if tangential) observation supporting an epochal discovery. To stretch this entropy analogy to the point of breaking, Bose-Einstein photonics are 'richer' than Fermi-Dirac electronics, at least from this narrow perspective.